

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS OF STRESSES IN SANDWICH STRUCTURES DUE TO THE BRAZIER EFFECT

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ABSTRACT

Some studies indicate that the cross-section of large wind turbine blades subjected to wind and gravity loads will ovalise due to the Brazier effects [1,2]. This feature could however not be verified by numerical experiments of a FE model of a fictive 61.5 m blade, based on the NREL 5MW reference turbine [3], subjected to simplified load cases. Accurate prediction of failure modes of sandwich structures based on finite element calculations are highly important if accurate predictions of such features in large wind turbine blades are to be investigated.

In this study, an experimental setup designed to cause deflection and stress patterns in the core similar to what might be achieved by the Brazier effect in a wind turbine blade subjected to severe wind loads has been carried out. The test set up will highlight stress in the through-thickness direction, causing classical shell theory to be circumspect as a modelling tool. By designing specimens with different foam core material properties, stiffness and strength, different failure modes were observed in the test. Through the use of combinations of solid and shell elements and geometrically nonlinear analyses, the experimental effects were shown to be predictable by an otherwise linear FE model.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Brazier effect, named after the author of some interwar period papers [4,5], is a nonlinear geometrical feature of slender thin-walled structures causing cross-sections to ovalise when the structure is subjected to bending loads, inducing through-thickness stresses in the core material of sandwich structures. The effect on wind turbine blades has been discussed extensively, for example by Jensen *et al* [6-8] and Chen *et al* [9]. In a parallel study, the NREL 5MW reference blade [3] has been subjected to simplified load cases in both flap- and edgewise directions in an attempt to verify the significance of the Brazier effect in wind turbine blade applications, but preliminary results tend to lean towards confirmation of the results by Chen *et al*, that the Brazier effect is not significant for this blade, see Fig. 1.

In this study, we are focussing on the sandwich part of the blade. Specifically, we attempt to verify the capability of our modelling in identifying the failure-driving phenomena and their relation to strength and stiffness of the core under the assumption that the sandwich panels resemble curved beams subjected to end forces. That is, outcomes from a finite element model of a coupon test is compared to test results of the same coupon, the coupon essentially being a curved beam. This simplified design was chosen in place of a more complex, multi-axial test setup such as have been reported in literature, eg. [10], because of limitations in manufacturing and testing facilities. Also, curved composite beams have been studied extensively [11-15] and so results can be compared to theoretical predictions.

Figure 1: Left: Deformation of cross section of 5MW blade under 2g edgewise loading (magnified by a factor 10). Right: Overview of blade model showing position of cross section.

This work has been partly conducted by students in the mandatory project course at the Computational Mechanics Master Programme at Chalmers University of Technology, whose full work is available in the report [16]. Two parallel projects studying the NREL 5MW blade have also been carried out [17-18]. The primary modelling tool used is geometrically nonlinear solid FEA using simplified failure criteria and linear orthotropic material models.

This paper is organized in the following way: Section 2 motivates the design of the tested structure, and Section 3 elaborates on the experimental part of the study. Section 4 then describes the finite element modelling work before the work is summed up by Results and Conclusions, sections 5 and 6.

2 TEST DESIGN

The criteria for the test specimen design was that a substantial deformation of the cross-section would occur and that the setup should emphasize the sensitivity to core material properties for the parameter study, preferably inducing several different failure modes of the sandwich structure. The initial idea, to subject a cylinder to three- or four point bending, was discarded in favour of a curved beam design as preliminary finite element simulations indicated that the limitations enforced by the geometry of the testing machine would cause all test specimen to fail from stress concentrations at the loading point, see further [16].

2.1 Design goals and limitations

The objective of this study was to investigate the influence of core strength and stiffness on the ultimate failure of a curved sandwich structure, as well as the quality of failure predictions, based on both FEM and handbook calculations. Specifically, the laminate plan was to be such that the weakest cores caused core-related failures, while the failure load levels for the stronger core structures was to be governed by the properties of the face material. To achieve this, a number of measures were taken: A series of preliminary FE models were used throughout the design procedure to predict possible

failure modes and ensure a sensitivity to core properties. A moderately large number of core materials, five, were used to ensure a wide spread in considered core properties. A division of the tests into three series was performed to allow for modifications of the testing procedure as more information was acquired.

2.1 Test design geometry

The final specimen design can be seen in Fig. 2. In the first test series, two specimen were tested at the same time to form a cylindrical section. The design was chosen to accommodate for clamping and negotiate stress concentrations occurring just below the loaded edge. The diameter was chosen as large as possible while still able to fit into the test machine used, the core material was chosen from DIAB:s Divinycell P and PX series to allow for thermoforming, with nominal densities ranging from 60 to 300 kg/m³. The expected outcome, based on preliminary FE analysis and handbook calculations [12], was that the sandwich structures with lighter cores would suffer core failure (or buckling/wrinkling) while the ones with heavier cores would suffer compressive laminate failure.

Figure 2: Above: Cross sectional layout plan of nominal test specimen. Below, left: Detail of flange layout. Below, right: Detail of layout at core chamfer.

Each ply (Fig. 2) consisted of a 0-90° mat of 300g/m² glass fibre assumed to be 0,5mm thick and consisting of 66% glass when cured; the thinnest glass fibre mat available at the shop where the test specimen were manufactured. The core was 15mm thick, a value chosen to ensure that the Px300 specimen (with the strongest and stiffest core) failed from compression of the laminate. Further properties of the different materials are shown in Table 1.

Core Properties	Unit	Px60	Px100	Px150	P150	Px300
P	[kg/m ³]	65	110	150	150	300
E ₁	[MPa]	6.9	25	63	152	180
E ₂	[MPa]		E ₁		E ₃	E ₁
E ₃	[MPa]	47	100	152	63	364
G ₁₂	[MPa]	6.6	19	32	40	85
U ₁₂	[-]	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.4
σ _{c1, compression}	[MPa]	0.28	0.80	1.40	2.30	4.20
τ ₁₂	[MPa]	0.24	0.70	1.00	1.25	2.00
Thermo forming effect on compression properties (only indicative)						
E ₁	[-]	1	1	1	0.77	1.15
σ _{c1, compression}	[-]	1	1	1	0.88	1.1

Table 1: Material properties of test specimen. The E₁, G₁₂ and strength properties are presented in DIAB data sheets [20], the other properties are based on a few tests and should only be considered as indicative. The face sheet lamina strength and stiffness properties for all specimen were E_f=22Gpa, σ_{f, compression}=264MPa and ε_{f, compression}=1.2%

2.3 Test series

To capture effects of material and manufacturing variability, a number of specimen were manufactured for each of the five core materials and divided into three different series of experiments.

The first series was manufactured and tested as a part of a course at Chalmers University of Technology [16]. The test specimen were manufactured by infusion using a polyester resin. Shrinkage in the polyester caused the flanges to angle out, with an average total flange deviation of 6.2°. The deviation introduced a bending moment when two beams where clamped together forming the test body, which caused the test body, planned to be circular, to be deformed before the load was applied in the test rig. Before the test started the inner horizontal diameter varied between 345 and 358mm and the inner vertical measures of the diameter were between 333 and 340mm, compared to the mould that had a diameter of 350 mm. For these tests, all measurements were performed under true symmetry, that is, two specimen such as the one shown in Fig. 2 were tested at the same time. Four different core materials were tested in this series, from Px60 through Px100 and Px150 to P150. Two samples each, making up one test each, with a width just over 100mm was performed for the softer cores Px60 and Px100, while the Px150 and P150 specimen were half as wide but twice as many such that four samples and two tests each were performed for those.

Figure 3: Flange geometry of specimen series 1, caused by shrinkage in the resin curing process.

In the second test series actions were taken to prevent the flanges to angle out, in order to prevent the test to be effected by the by an additional moment that is hard to control and calculate. Instead of a polyester, an epoxy resin was used to minimise resin shrinkage. To that end, a slight modification of the design at the corner of the flange, with a slightly larger corner radius, was also introduced. The geometry and manufacturing was also more controlled. Here, it was assumed that the test machine could support the structure alone, so each specimen was run separately. Beside the four different core materials from series 1, a fifth design using Px300 core was tested at this stage. Three specimen of Px60, two Px100 three Px150, one P150 and two Px300 were tested.

The third test series used the same type of specimen as in the second test, but with the addition that all experiments were run in parallel as in the first series to ensure that the apparent shift of failure point, see further the Results section below, was not an artefact of changed boundary conditions. One test, using two specimen, was run for each of the cores Px100, Px150, P150 and Px300.

3 EXPERIMENTS

The experiments were performed at DIAB's laboratories in Laholm, Sweden, during the spring of 2014 (series 1) and spring of 2015 (series 2 and 3).

3.1 Experimental setup

The tests were run on an Instron testing machine with a 25kN load cell, test speed was set to 10 mm/min and sampling rate 10 points/second. Cross head movement and applied load was tracked to yield force-displacement curves for each specimen; in series 1 and 3, these were however aggregate curves for two specimen. This was the reason that series 2 was run one specimen at a time. However, concerns were raised that the fixture in the test machine was not stiff enough, making the estimation of boundary conditions difficult and causing failure to occur away from the expected failure area, wherefore series 3 was tested symmetrically again. The off-centre failure points remained, though (cf. the Results section).

Figure 4: Test setup, example from series 1. The tests of series 3 were performed in the same manner, while for series 2, only one arch was tested at a time.

3.2 Evaluation method

The tests were evaluated primarily through the resulting load-displacement curves. Each test piece was also inspected manually post mortem; together with the load-displacement curves and theoretical predictions, this information was used to identify the mode of failure of the test piece. Video recordings of the course of the tests were also used in an attempt to identify primary and secondary failure modes, but unlike the high-speed camera recordings of *e.g.* [19], only a standard camera was used, which meant that identification was sometimes difficult and had to rely on predictions, see further Results section below.

4 FEM

The primary means of analysis used was the finite element method, allowing geometrical nonlinearity (large deformations) but assuming linear orthotropic material behaviour and adopting only engineering failure criteria (for example; the laminae are assumed to break when the strain exceeds 1,2%). The model, consisting of 5889 elements, with 5 elements in the through-thickness direction of the core, was prepared and results evaluated using SIEMENS pre- and postprocessor FEMAP, while NEi NASTRAN was used for the lion share of the computations¹. The solver was load-controlled, with at least 10 load steps. The algorithm was allowed to lower the step size if necessary, and a convergence study of five different mesh sizes was performed to ensure an appropriate mesh size.

4.1 Nominal FE model

Figure 5: Finite element model of test specimen. a) Entire model. b) Solid elements. c) Shell elements.

The two initial models were 50mm and 100mm wide, respectively, to cover the different specimen designs from series 1 elaborated on in section 2.3. Plies 1-3 and 14-16 (cf. Fig. 2), were modelled by laminate elements, while the rest of the model was built by solid elements; the core to allow investigation of through-thickness stresses and plies 4-13 for modelling reasons, to simplify the transition to the solid core. See also Fig. 5.

¹ MSC and NX NASTRAN analyses were also used. Results did not deviate much between solvers.

Rigid elements were furthermore used at the top edge of the upper flange to distribute a line load evenly between the inner and outer skin. The upper flange was furthermore restricted in all directions save down, while the lower flange was completely fixed.

4.2 Geometrical discrepancies

A simple linear interpolation was used to compensate for the effects caused by differences in width of the FE model analysed and the test specimen. To investigate the effect of the angled flanges described in section 2.3, a model with a 6.2° misalignment angle at the top flange was built. By simply enforcing the flanges to be aligned, significant strains and deformation were found from FEM, indicating that the specimen were already stressed at the onset of the tests.

4.3 Linear Failure Criteria

Figure 6: Failure criteria of sandwich beams.

Sandwich structures can fail in a number of different modes, as is shown schematically in Fig. 6. Instabilities of the nonlinear FE model was used as an indication of buckling mode failure; whether local or global indicated by the buckling shape. Linear buckling analysis was also run to evaluate stability. The laminates were assumed to break at a given strain level, while the core strength was described by stress levels². The levels used for the materials are given in Table 1.

As a compliment to this, handbook calculations of failure levels were also used. The formulas in this paragraph have been taken from Zenkert [11,12] and refer to straight beams unless stated otherwise. The Hoff formula (for isotropic face sheets) indicates that face wrinkling occurs at:

$$\sigma_w = 0.91 \sqrt[3]{E_f E_c G_c} \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_w = 0.5 t_f \sqrt[3]{E_f E_c G_c} \quad (2)$$

Where the second equation is modified based on experiments and t_f is the face thickness, while the

² Since the material model is linear, it would be easy to calculate equivalent stress levels. These were however the values used.

E's and the G's are the usual face and core material properties. Crimping is assumed to occur at

$$\sigma_{cr} = \frac{t_c G_c}{2t_f} \quad (2)$$

Furthermore, the bending efficiency factor for curved beams was analysed as a simplified metric of through-thickness core stresses indicating potential crushing of the core:

$$\eta_b = \frac{\hat{\sigma}_c R}{\hat{\sigma}_f t_f} \quad (3)$$

	Unit	Px60	Px100	Px150	P150	Px300
Face Sheet Wrinkling						
K_1	[-]	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
$\sigma_{f, wrinkling} = K_1 \cdot \sqrt{(E_f \cdot E_{c1} \cdot G_{c12})}$	[MPa]	50	109	177	256	348
$\epsilon_{f, wrinkling}$	[%]	0,23	0,50	0,80	1,16	1,58
Face Sheet Crimping						
$\sigma_{f, crimping} = t_c \cdot G_c / (2 \cdot t_f)$	[MPa]	102	295	496	620	1 318
$\epsilon_{f, crimping}$	[%]	0,47	1,34	2,25	2,82	5,99
Minimum Face Sheet strength						
$\sigma_{f, compression}$	[MPa]	50,03	109,31	176,99	255,71	264,00
$\epsilon_{f, compression}$	[%]	0,23	0,50	0,80	1,16	1,20
Stresses in the radial direction causing compression (or tensile) fracture of the core expressed as the "bending efficiency factor"						
η_b -(taking minimum face Strength)	[-]	1,91	2,50	2,71	3,08	5,44
η_b -(taking lamina face Strength)	[-]	0,36	1,04	1,81	2,98	5,44

Table 2: Failure levels of the different core materials with respect to handbook calculations of wrinkling, crimping and core crushing.

5 RESULTS

Results are presented in aggregate and overview forms to as large an extent possible because of limitations in terms of space. A division of results from the first and the latter two series has been made.

5.1 Series 1

The results from the first test series indicate that the FE method as applied in this project could predict the failure mode of the specimen with some accuracy, although the load levels were not well predicted because of the bending moments introduced by the angled flanges, as elaborated on in section 2.3. Further, the failures seemed to be located at the centre line, where the maximum moment of the beam occurs, indicating that the tapering and load transfer from the applied load to the intended failure region worked as planned. The sought-after effects were also identified and it was believed that more careful manufacturing of test specimen would address the problem of load level prediction. Thus, as the failure modes shown in Fig. 7 were accurately predicted (see [16]), further evaluation of series 1 was deemed unnecessary and focus shifted to series 2 and 3.

Figure 7: Four specimen with similar geometry and glass fibre skins but with different foam core materials from Divinycell P and Px series. From left to right: Skin wrinkling leading into crushing of core (Px60), skin wrinkling leading to delamination (Px100), core shear fracture (Px150) and laminate compression breakage (P150). The vertical midpoint is marked with a black line.

5.2 Series 2 and 3

Series 2 and 3 share the feature that all of the experimental results indicate that failure occurred at a 22.5° angle from the centre line, see Fig. 8. An attempted explanation of this is given in Fig. 11. Series 3 was set up symmetrically to mimic series 1 to rule out changes in boundary condition as a cause for this shift of breaking point. Table 3 shows a failure mode analysis, which indicates that wrinkling is the likely failure initiator for the softer cores, although secondary failure modes differ, while the stiffer ones fail from core shear and laminate compression, respectively. Load displacement curves are compared in Fig. 9 for FEM and test. The FEA was loaded with the maximum load from the test.

Figure 8: All specimen tested in series 2 (single unsymmetrical) and 3 (double symmetrical). From left to right: three pieces of Px60 from series 2, two pieces of Px100 from series 2 and two from series 3, three pieces of Px150 from series 2 and two from series 3, one piece of P150 from series 2 and two from series 3 and finally two pieces of Px300 from series 2 and two from series 3.

Figure 9: Results from testing compared to FEM, series 2 and 3.

Test results from series 2	Unit	Px60	Px100	Px150	P150	Px300
Maximum Force	[N]	256	544	820	950	1250
Stress and Failure evaluation with FEA - applied load is the failure load - >1 indicates possible failure mode						
Face Sheet - Minor Principal Lamina Strain	[%]	0,315	0,709	1,08	1,25	1,68
Core - Maximum 12 Shear Stress	[MPa]	0,22	0,543	0,843	1,02	1,4
Core - Minimum Principal Stress	[MPa]	0,75	0,87	1,38	1,54	3,9
Buckling Load - Linear FEA	[N]	335,7	674,8	1083	1534	2145
FEA Result / Material or Buckling Strength (>1 indicates possible failure mode)						
Core Shear Stress	[-]	0,92	0,78	0,84	0,93	0,70
Core Compression Stress	[-]	2,68	1,09	0,99	0,67	0,93
Face Sheet Lamina Stress	[-]	0,26	0,59	0,90	1,04	1,40
Face Sheet Wrinkling	[-]	1,39	1,43	1,34	1,08	1,06
Face Sheet Crimping	[-]	0,68	0,53	0,48	0,44	0,28
Eigen Value Buckling FEA / Failure Load	[-]	0,76	0,81	0,76	0,62	0,58

Table 3: Failure analysis of series 2 and three. Possible results from post mortem inspection of test pieces indicated by colour. Light red indicate initiation failure mode and orange secondary failure.

Figure 10: Stress levels and angle where laminate plan is likely to instigate instabilities.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a study of failure of sandwich structures, specifically with respect to changes in core material properties, has been presented. Geometrically nonlinear FEM analysis with linear material models using simplified handbook failure criteria has been shown to fairly accurately predict failure mode.

A total of 31 curved sandwich beams have been manufactured and tested to failure, using five different core materials. The tests were divided into three separate series to allow for compensation of testing malpractices over the course of the study.

The first test series saw failure at the point of the beam where the bending moment is greatest, as was planned, but at lower load levels than anticipated from FE predictions. It was believed that the lower than expected failure loads were due to that the flanges of the specimen were angling out; this phenomena was studied and shown to influence the behaviour of the test significantly.

The second and third series, consisting of specimen carefully manufactured not to angle out, saw failure instead at about 22.5° angle away from the point of maximum moment, likely because the layup, designed to distribute the load application at the core material, had a thickness drop in this area, cf. Fig. 10. It is believed this thickness drop may also have instigated initiation points for instabilities, which could help explain why the laminate failure modes also seem to initiate here. This also lead to the conclusion that the feature was not seen in the first series because of the pre stress caused by the moment required to straighten the flanges.

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